

POSTMODERNISM AND THE STAGES OF ITS DEVELOPMENT

Mukhlisa V. Tursunova

Uzbekistan State World Languages University, independent researcher.

email: mukhlisa_vakhobovna@list.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11031274>

Abstract: The research is intended to briefly examine the expansion of postmodernism as a contemporary philosophical and literary-critical movement. The study is expected to assist more understanding about the trend by chronologically dividing it into some specific periods. The research paper considers a number of critical, philosophical and literary-aesthetic works to bring it into some effective comprehensible periodization.

Key words: expansion, postmodernism, contemporary, trend, chronological division, critical, philosophical, literary-aesthetic, periodization.

The process of studying several sources showed that the development of postmodernism can be studied chronologically in four stages:

1. The first stage is the period of fundamental formation of postmodernism, covering 1940-50s.

2. The second stage is the period of popularization of postmodernism, and the 1960-70s can be classified within this stage.

3. The third stage – corresponding to 1980-2000s, this period can be called the peak of postmodernism.

4. The last fourth stage covers the period from 2000 to the present, and in these years, there was a decline in postmodernism.

The formation of postmodernism as a literary trend can be linked to the works of several worldly acclaimed playwrights and writers “post” second world war period due to their literary-aesthetic style that was particularly different from previous gigantic literary movement of modernism [Nicole, 51]. This was specifically prevalent in the works of Samuel Beckett, Jorge Luis Borges and William Seward Burroughs. Samuel Beckett founded postmodern silence in his famous play “Waiting for Godot”. Jorge Luis Borges’s legacy is characterized by postmodern artistic qualities such as a complex and fragmented narrative style, stories combining several layers of time and space, crossing the boundaries between the “real” reality and literature. William Seward Burroughs’s “Naked Lunch” exposes all the vices, stupidities and crimes in Western culture, especially in postmodern American society after the Second World War.

During the second phase, postmodernism began to be interpreted in a wide variety of fields such as a philosophy, literary theory and culture. First, in

the 1960s, general descriptive conclusions given to critical correspondences that reflected the cultural values of developed countries [Brooker, 22] started to be called postmodern or postmodernism. In literature, metafiction as an analogical term to postmodernism [Hutcheon, ix] has been introduced. Metafiction succeeded in interpreting the world as a text thus critically investigating the power of literature as well.

Literary scholars mark the peak of postmodern movement with French philosopher, Jean-François Lyotard and his work "Postmodern Condition" and admit him as the father of postmodernism. Based on Lyotard's views, the postmodernism trend is a set of ideas that reflect the postmodern situation that prevailed in the postmodern era. His such analyses clarify the term "postmodern" itself and several terms related to it.

From the 2000s to the present day is defined as the last phase of postmodernism. Although several works were created in this period, in general there was a significant decline in it. Due to the fact that the endless pursuit of knowledge, critical views of history, artistic-literary elements of metafiction and the ironic approaches welcomed by postmodernists started to be highlighted only in some cases, postmodernism has fallen to the second level among the higher intellectual levels. It was as well caused by such factors such as carelessness, extreme anxiety and fanaticism of the early XXI century.

References:

1. Brooker P. Modernism/Postmodernism. – USA. Routledge., 2014 – P. 22
2. Hutcheon L. A Poetics of Postmodernism. – USA. Routledge., 1988. – P. ix.
3. Nicole B. The Cambridge Introduction to Postmodern Fiction. – UK. Cambridge University Press., 2009. – P. 51.

